

SMART TOURISM – IN PRESENT

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Abstract

This article deals with such concepts as smart tourism, E-tourism, smart society, virtual tour. Modern society is a smart society, which is well versed in informational technologies and uses them in everyday and professional life. Smart society is represented by the users of various portable and mobile devices. Smart-tourism combines tourism experience with informational technologies. The multifaceted use of information technology is what characterizes a smart society. The concept of smart tourism is represented by five elements: accessibility, accommodation, amenities, attractions, activities. The development of the tourism industry in a smart society is expressed through a new form - electronic tourism (E-tourism). E-tourism is one of the most popular and attractive areas in the economy. Informational technologies are at the base of e-tourism. Virtual touring is the most developed area of E-tourism today. Constant development, improvement, innovation in the world of information technology contributes to the growth of the attractiveness of smart tourism.

Keywords: smart tourism, E-tourism, smart society, information technology, virtual tour.

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Lately, we have often been hearing new expressions containing the word smart such as smart home, smart health, smart retails, smart mobility, smart tourism and so on. These expressions describing our reality and are gradually and firmly entering our everyday life and professional activities.

Now we are seeing how the electronic society is entering the smart stage, that is, a smart society is being formed. At the smart stage, information flows become fundamentally different and technologies get the opportunity to interact with the outside world directly without human participation. Technologies become able to collect information about the real world and turn it into knowledge suitable for practical use. A smart society is a society in which informational technologies are used to transform economic, social and managerial processes by optimizing, automating them and enabling collective activity. [1, c. 165-167]

The concept of "smart" tourism was formed on the basis of the concepts of "smart planet" and "smart city". Smart-tourism combines the tourism experience with informational technology, allowing you to personalize information for a specific user (to present information that is relevant to a particular tourist) [2].

The concept of Smart Tourism is defined by the European Union as a destination facilitating access to tourism and hospitality products, services, spaces and experiences through Information and communications technologies.

The concept of smart tourism emerged as a result of the adoption of the Directive of the European Union on smart tourism. [3]

Smart tourism as a concept includes five main elements (Five A) [3]:

1. Accessibility - refers to how digitally or physically accessible a city or area is. Tourist information centers are the focus of this concept. Accessibility is one of the important components of smart tourism. Accessibility can be viewed in different ways/aspects. The first aspect is physical accessibility. Physical accessibility is the availability of public transport, transport categories, fares, providing conditions for the movement of people with special needs in a city or a certain area. The second aspect refers to digital technologies that can offer information about the services provided in all languages.

2. Accommodation - an ideal tourist environment and an efficient infrastructure for tourists.
3. Amenities - means all the additional services provided by a tourist destination.
4. Attractions - visiting places that have history or distinctive and attractive characteristics.
5. Activities - organization of various events, excursions.

Most people appreciate the benefits of using informational technology in a variety of human activities. Informational technology has become very simple and clear to use for the final user, has a friendly interface, and is time saving.

The multifaceted use of informational technologies is what describes a smart society and is the main characteristic of it. In many ways, innovations in tourism are due to the emergence of the informational society, which forms a digital, virtual reality with specific social, cultural, and consumer practices.[4]

Informational technologies have also filled the tourism services gap.

It is necessary to note the factors affecting the digitalization of tourism [5]:

1. global digitalization;
2. the formation of a new type of digital traveler;
3. new business technologies;
4. remote access to services;
5. personalization of services for the client.

Smart tourism is primarily perceived as the use of IT tools and applications. Mobile devices are an integral part of today's generation of tourists. These devices and informational technologies provide quick access to tourist services and information. The current direction in smart tourism is the development of mobile applications. Mobile applications allow you to personalize the search for the necessary information as much as possible.

The development of the tourism industry in a smart society is expressed through a new form - electronic tourism (e-Tourism).

Informational technologies represent the basis of E-tourism: software for creating websites, software for creating virtual tours, photo processing and video editing software, payment systems, mobile technologies, communication technologies and other systems. The new informational technologies contribute to the introduction of E-tourism.

E-tourism refers to the electronic distribution of travel services.

E-tourism is an online service that provides direct sales of tourism services to end consumers and brings together tour operators, travel agents and intermediaries.[6]

Tourism services are specific, most often individualized products that are purchased by the clients via the Internet at a distance. Sales in E-tourism depend on the quality and visual appeal of online materials.

E-tourism is becoming more and more popular every year as it reduces various expenses for travelers and saves time on transport and movement. E-tourism is one of the most popular and profitable areas in the economy.

Electronic tourism (E-tourism) implies the transition of all processes and value chains in tourism industries, travel, hospitality and catering to digital technologies that enable organizations to work as efficiently as possible. Examples of best practices for using tools and applications are [7]:

1. The introduction of sensor technologies at the location, which create information, help to store and send data.
2. Creating an integrated solution for boosting mobility and interaction of the tourist with the destination.
3. Free and stable Wi-Fi connection for tourists.

4. Development of smartphone and tablet applications for product search and services at destinations.

5. Use of QR codes, facilitating tourists interaction with the location.

6. Geolocation systems, that help tourists find the location of all attractions.

7. Control system traffic in real time, supplemented with suggestions on optimal routes.

The most attractive areas of e-tourism today are museum exhibits and virtual tours.

In general, virtual tours are realistic displays of a three-dimensional multi-element space that replaces real traveling. Some concepts of virtual tourism includes the term virtual tour. Virtual tourism is a type of activity of individuals and legal entities that organize or make virtual tours. [4]

Well-designed virtual tours make it possible to interest and attract Internet users to museums and various kinds of tourist routes. Perhaps some users will want to visit the sights live.

Virtual tourism means “moving” to an arbitrarily remote, but real-life place.

Virtual excursions (tours) in Moldova are provided by the portal *visit.md*. The portal *visit.md* provides tours in different directions: monasteries, museums, fortresses, estates, winemaking.

In leading tourism companies, innovation is programmed and is a standard component when deciding on further development. [4]

Conclusion

Constant development, improvement, innovation in the world of informational technologies contribute to the growth of the attractiveness of smart tourism. The transition to the digitalization of the tourism industry is a new stage in the development of smart travel services that make it easier to search, order and purchase a tourist product, saving valuable time. Virtual tours will become one of the tourism consumption products in the future presented in different formats due to the behavior and desire of the consumer.

The future of the tourism industry largely depends on an innovation-driven tourism policy.

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